

Scientific paper on household characteristics and consumption patterns

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Document Overview

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10-11-2025	v.01	Silvia Tomasi	Submission to Ecological Economics
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26-11-2025	v.01	Silvia Tomasi	Submission to Cleaner and Responsible Consumption
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About the project

Cities concentrate high density socio-economic activities, consuming 70% of global resources, producing 60-80% of anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and generating waste of resources, energy and water. This is a critical issue, but at the same time an opportunity.

Circular economy models can reduce this waste and reduce human environmental impacts.

ECLECTIC brings circular economy from theory to action in cities, by improving the understanding of cities as complex multi-level ecosystems with inputs, outputs, and resource flows. The project designs, implements, and monitors strategic action plans for circular economy in cities, taking care to address vulnerable groups needs and reduce inequality in selecting circular models benefiting them.

Four city-region living labs (CiRLabs) located in Italy, Lithuania, Sweden and Portugal will be the testing sites where the circular practices will be implemented. In the CiRLabs, stakeholder engagement processes will be the means to identify needs and visions and select circular economy strategies that fit them. KPIs will be defined to measure the circular economy action plans.

Outputs will include four scientific papers, three reports, four actionable reports, a toolbox, workshops and trainings.

Project partners

Abstract

The transition to a sustainable circular economy requires the widespread adoption of circular consumption behaviours, yet little is known about how these behaviours are distributed across society, and whether this distribution is equitable. The contribution of individuals and households — through behaviours such as repairing, hiring maintaining— is crucial but often overlooked, overshadowed by contributions by industrial sectors. In particular, the role of vulnerable households, affected by economic, social, and structural disadvantages, has not been systematically examined, even though both the constraints and opportunities posed by the circular economy may be amplified for them. This study investigates how individuals contribute to the circular economy transition through their engagement in circular consumption behaviours and examines the extent of inequalities in such engagement. Using data from the 2022 Household Budget Survey in Italy and Portugal and applying a regression approach combined with a propensity score matching model integrated by household vulnerability archetypes, this study analyses patterns of engagement in circular consumption behaviours across socio-economic groups. Results show that households characterized by higher income, better education, younger age, and male household heads are more likely to engage in circular consumption behaviours, while vulnerability constitutes a substantial barrier to engagement in the circular economy suggesting that the circular economy may extend existing advantages and perpetuate socio-economic inequalities. These findings extend previous research on the contribution of individuals to the circular economy by integrating a social equity perspective and highlight the need for policies that ensure equitable access to circular economy opportunities.

Keywords

Circular Economy, Circular Consumption Behaviour, Vulnerability, Households, Household Budget Survey, Propensity Score Matching

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